

Unveiling Quartinizib: A Comprehensive Narrative Review of an Emerging Anti-Cancer Therapy

Babiker Bashir Haroun Baraka^{1*}, CH Snigdha Varsha², Saumya³, S.Vignesh⁴

¹*Department of Pharmacology, KLE College of Pharmacy, Rajajinagar, Bangalore-560010, Karnataka, India*

^{2,3,4}*Department of Pharmacy Practice, KLE College of Pharmacy, Rajajinagar, Bangalore-560010, Karnataka, India*

*Corresponding author

Mr. Babiker Bashir Haroun Baraka

Ph. D. Research Scholar

Department of Pharmacology,

KLE College of Pharmacy Bengaluru – 560010, Karnataka

Abstract

Acute myeloid leukemia (AML) is a bone marrow cancer with FLT3/ITD mutations, which are present in 25-30% of adult AML patients. These mutations lead to uncontrolled cell proliferation and decreased overall survival rates. Quizartinib, a selective second-generation type II FLT3 inhibitor, has shown potential in treating FLT3-ITD AML by binding to the inactive FLT3-ITD receptor with high affinity. Clinical studies have shown that quizartinib increases survival and remission rates among individuals with relapsed/refractory AML. Quizartinib was approved in Japan on May 25, 2023, and by the FDA on July 20, 2023. It has shown greater effectiveness over existing FLT3 inhibitors and substantial selectivity for the FLT3/ITD mutant receptor. Treatment for refractory or relapsed AML with quizartinib is safe and effective, with adverse effects including gastrointestinal discomfort, myelosuppression, infections, constitutional issues, and bleeding. Its development and approval mark a significant step forward in the targeted treatment of acute myeloid leukemia, offering patients a more focused and potentially more effective therapeutic option. Ongoing research and clinical trials will continue to refine the use of quizartinib and similar targeted therapies, aiming to improve overall survival rates and quality of life for acute myeloid leukemia patients.

Keywords: Acute myeloid leukemia, FLT3-ITD, Quizartinib, and Clinical Trial

Introduction

Acute myeloid leukemia (AML) is a bone marrow malignancy characterized by the premature arrest of hematopoietic precursors.^[1] Although FMS-like tyrosine kinase-3 internal tandem duplication (FLT3/ITD) mutations have been found in AML patients since 1996, the precise nature of treatment for this particular condition is yet unknown. FLT3/ITD AML was first identified fifteen years ago and is now recognized as a unique clinical entity. This kind of AML is often fatal and presents significant challenges for those of us who treat it. To help us understand why these individuals relapse so fast and how to support them, it may be helpful to take into account some new clinical and analytical results on this condition.^[2]

The percentage of adult AML patients with FLT3/ITD mutations was about 25%.^[2] Approximately 2% to 3% of all cancer cases in India are acute myeloid leukemia (AML), which has a grim prognosis and therapy. It's the primary cause of hematopoietic cancers in the world. AML accounts for 70% of adult leukemia cases. In 2020, there were 269,503 new cases of leukemia in males and 205,016 new cases in females, according to GLOBOCAN 2020, which provides global estimates of cancer incidence and death for developing nations. Males and females died at an estimated rate of 176,000 and 132,000, respectively. To achieve complete remission (CR), it's essential to identify the cancer early and commence induction chemotherapy. One to two percent of cancer cases in India are AML. The overall five-year survival (OS) for AML is 28.3%, which indicates that the prognosis is still not good. Patients under 50 years old with newly diagnosed AML have an OS of 40-50%, compared to 5-10% for the elderly.^[3]

The most prevalent genetic mutation in AML is the internal tandem duplication mutation of the FMS-like receptor tyrosine kinase 3 (FLT3-ITD), which is linked to a high leukemic rate and a poor prognosis. It is found in about 30% of AML patients.^[4] Mutations in the FLT3-ITD protein take place in the juxtamembrane region, disrupting the auto-inhibitory activity and leading to kinase activation. FLT3-ITD kinase activity leads to unregulated cell growth, survival, and differentiation. FLT3-ITD mutations affect the pathways such as PI3K/AKT, MAPK/ERK, and JAK/STAT increase the chances of recurrence, and decrease overall survival.^[5] FMS-like tyrosine kinase 3 (FLT3) has been identified as a potential therapeutic target for acute myeloid leukemia (AML).^[6] This class III receptor tyrosine kinase is often found in the bone marrow of primordial hematopoietic cells. To treat AML patients, several small-molecule tyrosine kinase inhibitors that specifically target FLT3 have been developed. Based on its mechanism of binding to FLT3, FLT3 inhibitors are categorized as type 1 and type 2. Type 1 inhibitors bind to the FLT3 receptor in the active conformation close to the activation loop or the ATP binding domain. Examples of these inhibitors are midostaurin, gilteritinib, lestaurtinib, and crenolanib. Type 1 drugs effectively suppress both FLT3-ITD and FLT3-TKD. Type 2 inhibitors, including quizartinib and sorafenib, bind to the FLT3 receptor in an inactive form at the ATP-binding domain. Most FLT3-TKD mutations do not respond to type 2 inhibitors because they alter the active kinase conformation of FLT3.^[7]

Quizartinib is a strong and selective second-generation type II FLT3 inhibitor that binds to the receptor's inactive kinase conformation and inhibits FLT3-ITD in acute myeloid leukemia patients with up to 10 times more affinity than other tyrosine kinase receptors.^[8, 9] It was approved in Japan on May 25th, 2023 for the treatment of R/R FLT3-ITD mutated AML and approved by the Food and Drug Administration on July 20, 2023, for the treatment of newly diagnosed acute myeloid leukemia (AML) that is FLT3 internal tandem duplication (ITD)-positive.^[10, 11]

History of the Quizartinib

Small molecule FLT3 kinase inhibitors have been investigated as potential treatments for AML patients; however they lack efficacy, oral pharmacokinetics, and tolerability. Compound 7 (AC220) was discovered as the most effective and specific FLT3 inhibitor, with an ideal oral PK profile and superior effectiveness in tumor xenograft models.^[12] The result AC220 was designated as quizartinib, the first compound developed specifically as an oral FLT3 inhibitor for potential therapeutic use in FLT3/ITD AML. Quizartinib was introduced into the literature in 2009.^[13] Ambit Biosciences developed Quizartinib (AC220), which was purchased by Daiichi Sankyo in 2014.^[5]

Chemistry of the Quizartinib

Chemically, Quizartinib is a benzoimidazothiazole. It belongs to phenyl urea, isoxazole, and morpholines families of medicines^[14]. Quizartinib dihydrochloride is a white to off-white solid. It has the molecular formula of $C_{29}H_{32}N_6O_4S \cdot 2 HCl$ and a 560.7 for the free base and a molecular weight of 633.6 for the salt. In the molecule, urea has one amino group replaced with a 5- tert-butyl-1,2-oxazol-3-yl group, whilst the other has an imidazole at the para-position to replace the phenyl group[2,1-b].Benzothiazol-2-yl group, which is then replaced by a 2-(morpholine-4-yl)ethoxy group at position 7. This drug is given orally^[11]. Solubility: With an increase in pH, water solubility of quizartinib hydrochloride (pKa 4.75 and 3.16) falls. It is very slightly soluble in aqueous fluids at pH 1, but substantially insoluble at pH 2 and above. Quizartinib Hydrochloride is sparingly soluble in ethanol^[11].

The chemical structure of quizartinib dihydrochloride is

Figure.1: Chemical structure of Quizartinib^[15]

Characteristics of the Quizartinib

Though various medications for the treatment of acute myeloid leukemia were being tested, such as midostaurin, sorafenib, lestaurtinib, tandutinib, and sunitinib, Quizartinib was introduced in the literature in 2009. Quizartinib's selective nature towards the FLT3 gene made it different from the other drugs. The initial adapted medications failed as stand-alone treatments due to the substantial FLT3 inhibition necessary for bone marrow blasts and prolonged inhibition for apoptosis. At FLT3 inhibitory doses in vivo, they were intolerable due to their expected off-target effects. Moreover, many had suboptimal pharmacokinetic properties, such as increased plasma protein binding, and low half-life that led to reduced efficacy. An original phage display screening technique was used to identify a bis-aryl urea derivative as a strong and specific FLT3 inhibitor. Although this lead chemical was very selective and powerful for FLT3, it was optimized to increase its pharmacokinetic profile and water solubility by adding a solubilizing morpholinoethoxy group in place of a carboxamide group. As a result, AC220 was discovered and developed specifically as an oral FLT3 inhibitor with the potential to treat FLT3/ITD AML. This molecule was later named quizartinib. Quizartinib is significantly more selective for FLT3, and specifically the FLT3/ITD mutant receptor, than various compounds that are often utilized as FLT3 inhibitors, per the method of its isolation. In clinical trials, sorafenib and lestaurtinib were both severely limited by toxicity and quizartinib is expected to have a significant advantage in this area. As an FLT3 inhibitor, quizartinib was thoroughly investigated in mouse xenograft models, primary blast tissues, and cell lines. Quizartinib decreased phosphorylated FLT3 and promoted apoptosis with an IC₅₀ of 1-2 nM in experiments employing MV4-11 or Molm14 cells (all of which express FLT3/ITD mutant receptors) as well as blasts derived from FLT3/ITD acute myeloid leukemia patients. Surprisingly, quizartinib continued to be slightly successful against FLT3 in human plasma. Since the majority of small molecule kinase inhibitors are strongly protein-bound and extremely hydrophobic, a low nanomolar IC₅₀ in a culture medium which normally contains just 10%

serum does not correspond to a similar efficacy in plasma. Compared to other inhibitors, quizartinib has a minimum of 25 times greater potency against FLT3 in plasma ^[13].

Table 1: Pharmacokinetic Parameters of the Quizartinib ^[11]

PK parameters	
Absorption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The study discovered that quizartinib, a medicine used to treat acute myeloid leukemia, has an average absolute bioavailability of 71% in healthy people. ✓ In healthy subjects fasting, the Tmax of quizartinib and AC886 were around 4 hours and 5 to 6 hours after oral administration, respectively. ✓ The Cmax and AUC0-24h in patients who were newly diagnosed with acute myeloid leukemia were determined to be 140 ng/mL (71%) and 2,680 ng.h/mL (85%) during induction therapy, and 204 ng/mL (64%) and 3,930 ng.h/mL (78%) during consolidation therapy, respectively. ✓ For the metabolite AC886, the estimated Cmax and AUC0-24h were as follows: during induction therapy, 163 ng/mL (52%) and 3,590 ng.h/mL (51%) were recorded; during consolidation therapy, 172 ng/mL (47%) and 3,800 ng.h/mL (46%) were recorded. ✓ There were no variations clinically in the pk profile of quizartinib when given with a high fat and calorie meal.
Volume of distribution	In healthy individuals, it was determined to be 275L (17%).
Protein binding	In vitro plasma protein binding of quizartinib and AC886 is 99% or higher.
Metabolism	Quizartinib is largely metabolized by oxidation by CYP3A4/5.
Elimination	feces (unchanged) and urine
Clearance	The estimated body clearance of quizartinib in healthy participants was 2.23 L/hour (29%)
Half-life	During maintenance treatment, individuals who were newly diagnosed with AML had mean half-life of 81 hours (\pm 73) for quizartinib.

Pharmacodynamics of Quizartinib

Quizartinib inhibited tumour growth in a rodent model of FLT3-ITD-dependent leukemia. In vitro investigations have revealed that quizartinib is a potent inhibitor of the slow delayed rectifier potassium current (IKs). A concentration-dependent QTcF interval lengthening of 18–24 ms was anticipated by the exposure-response analysis for the mean steady-state Cmax of quizartinib at dosage levels of 26.5 mg and 53 mg during maintenance treatment ^[11].

Mechanism of action

FLT3 receptor tyrosine kinase is inhibited by the relatively small drug quizartinib. Both quizartinib and its main active metabolite AC886 bind to FLT3's adenosine triphosphate (ATP) binding domain with a similar degree of affinity. In a binding experiment, however, both drugs' affinity for the FLT3-ITD mutant was ten times lower than that of FLT3. Inhibiting FLT3 kinase activity,

quizartinib and AC886 prevented the receptor from becoming auto-phosphorylated. This prevented subsequent FLT3 receptor signaling and stopped FLT3-ITD-dependent cell proliferation^[11].

Pre-Clinical Study of the Quizartinib

The study identified that 33% of patients had primary refractory AML, 47% had an NPM1 mutation, and over one-third had at least 0.5 FLT3-ITD variant allele frequencies. For quizartinib, the average Survival was 6.2 months, while for chemotherapy, it was 4.7 months (hazard ratio 0.76, $p = 0.02$). The widely observed adverse events were febrile neutropenia (33%), and QTc prolongation (26%, grade 1-2)^[15].

Phases of Clinical Trial

a. Phase 1 trial

Six healthy male volunteers received a 60 mg oral solution of quizartinib as a monotherapy agent in the first phase of clinical trial. The outcomes of the study demonstrated that quizartinib exhibited outstanding safety and tolerability in healthy males. Jorge et al. conducted a Phase I multicentre dosage-escalation study on 76 patients with Relapsed/Refractory AML, administering quizartinib at a daily dose of 12-450 mg over 28 days. During the initial 28 days of the research, concurrent use of hydroxyurea was permitted for a maximum of 5 days at a dosage of 5 g/day. This study found that the maximum tolerated dosage (MTD) was 200 mg/day. In addition, another Phase 1 study conducted by Altman et al. showed that the MTD, used together with onset and strengthening chemotherapy, was 60 mg/day. In a different Phase I clinical study, individuals with AML undergoing allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation were treated with quizartinib monotherapy as a supportive treatment. In this clinical research, quizartinib was administered orally in 28-day cycle. 60 mg was the highest dosage given for treatment. These trials have demonstrated that quizartinib has a favourable tolerance profile and a manageable level of safety^[15].

b. Phase 2 Trial

Six clinical trials with quizartinib for acute myeloid leukemia have been conducted in this phase; two of these studies were for relapsed/refractory acute myeloid leukemia and five of the studies were for AML with the FLT3-ITD mutation. To find out the safety profile and effect of quizartinib, 333 patients with relapsed or resistant acute myeloid leukemia were divided into two groups in a study by Jorge et al. Group 1 comprised of 60 years or older patients who had received first-line treatment within a year, and Group 2 included patients 18 years or older who had received salvage chemotherapy or hematopoietic stem cell transplantation. All patients had an FLT3-ITD mutation, and quizartinib doses were 135 mg/d for males and 90 mg/d for females during 28-day treatment cycles that continued until relapse. The composite complete remission rates were equal among 332 assessable patients with FLT3-ITD-positive and those with less than 10% allelic frequency, but lower in those with undetectable FLT3-ITD mutations. The mean total mortality for patients with a positive FLT3-ITD mutation was equivalent in the first and second groups, at 25+4 weeks for the first and 24 weeks for the latter group^[18]. Another randomized, open-label, two-dosing regimen Phase IIb clinical trial assessed the potency and safety of quizartinib in 76 patients who had FLT3-ITD mutations that had previously undergone transplantation or second-line remedial treatment. These participants were given quizartinib at a dose of 30 mg or 60 mg daily based on randomization^[19]. The findings revealed that the composite full remission rates in both groups were 47%. It was demonstrated that a 60 mg daily dosage is more beneficial than a 30 mg daily dose. Cytopenias (anaemia 21.1%, thrombocytopenia 10.5%), nausea 10.5%, tiredness 13.2%, febrile neutropenia 10.5%, and dysgeusia 10.5% were the most common side effects among those taking 30 mg/day and nausea (22.2%), absolute neutropenia was 11.1%, and vomiting was 11.1% was common among those taking 60 mg/day^[15].

c. Phase 3 Trial

Patients aged 18 and above with FLT3-ITD Relapsed/Refractory AML were enrolled in the QUANTUM-R experiment. The investigator's choice of one of three preselected salvage chemotherapy regimens or single-agent quizartinib was administered to patients in a 2:1 randomization. The daily oral dose of quizartinib was raised from 30 mg to 60 mg, if no QTc prolongation was observed. Those using strong CYP3A inhibitors were prescribed a lower starting dose of quizartinib was 20 mg once daily, which

was then escalated to 30 mg once daily if the same QTc interval specifications were achieved. Between the year 2014 and 2017, 367 patients were recruited, with 245 assigned to quizartinib and 122 to salvage chemotherapy. The average patient age was 55 and 57 years, respectively. The study found that 33% of patients had primary refractory AML, 47% had an NPM1 mutation, and over one-third had at least 0.5 FLT3-ITD variant allele frequency. For quizartinib, the average Survival was 6.2 months, while for chemotherapy, it was 4.7 months (hazard ratio 0.76, p = 0.02). The most occurred adverse events were febrile neutropenia (33%), and OTc prolongation (26%, grade 1-2).^[7]

Table 2: Summary of clinical trial phases of quizartinib with chemotherapy^[16]

Clinical trial Gov. identifier	Trial (phases)	Eligible age for study (number)	Characteristics of disease	Chemotherapy	Response rate (clinical)
NCT03552029	1	18 and above (156)	AML with FLT3-ITD(+)	Quizartinib+milademetan, 20 or 30 mg quizartinib	Recruiting without any results
NCT01390337	1	18 -60 years (19)	diagnosed with AML newly	Increased doses of AC220 7+3 cytarabine and Daunorubicin	OR: 84%
NCT01892371	1 or 2	18 and above(72)	AML and MDS	Quizartinib started concomitantly with azacitidine/cytarabine Phase I: 60 mg daily of a 28-day cycle and phase II: maximum tolerated dose from Phase I.	OR:67% MS:14.8 months
NCT03661307	1 or 2	18 and above (52)	AML with FLT3-ITD(+)	Decitabine: 20 mg/m ² /d by vein on days 1–10 Quizartinib: 40 mg/d by mouth every day beginning on day 5 of cycle 1	Recruiting without any results
NCT03135054	2	18 and above(40)	AML carrying FLT3-ITD(+)	Omacetaxine mepesuccinate+quizartinib Quizartinib 30 mg daily continuously (28 days)	Recruiting without any results
NCT02668653	3	18-75 years (536)	Diagnosis(newly) of AML with FLT3-ITD(+)	Induction: 2 cycles cytarabine and daunorubicin/idarubicin Consolidation: 4 cycles of cytarabine Maintenance: 12 cycles experimental quizartinib	Recruiting without any results

drNCT03735875	2b or 3	18 and above (32)	AML with FLT3-ITD mutations	Quizartinib 30 mg and Venetoclax 400 mg daily given orally	Recruiting without any results
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Table 3: Summary of clinical trial phases of quizartinib as a single agent ^[16]

(myelodysplastic syndrome), OR (overall response), CR (complete remissions), PRs (partial remissions), MS (median survival), OS (overall survival).

		older (17)	refractory AML	doses of AC220	
NCT00462761	1	18 years and older (76)	Regardless of FLT3 status - Relapsed or refractory AML	14 days	OR: 30% (CR: 13%, PRs: 17%) MS: 14 weeks
NCT01468467	1	18 years and older (13)	Maintenance therapy after allogeneic stem transplant treatment	28 days a cycle with 24 continuous treatment cycles	OS: 13–142 weeks 69% patients ≥50 weeks 31% patients >2 year
NCT02984995	2	20 years and older (38)	AML with FLT3-ITD(+) - Relapsed or refractory	Once a day (daily)	Without results
NCT01565668	2b	18 years and older (76)	AML with FLT3-ITD(+) - Relapsed or refractory	28 days cycle	OR: 30 mg group: 61% 60 mg group: 71%
NCT02039726	3	18 years and older (367)	AML with FLT3-ITD(+) - Relapsed or refractory	20 mg or 30 mg of quizartinib	Median OS: 27 weeks

NCT03746912	Expanded treatment	18 years and above (adult and older adults)	AML with FLT3-ITD mutations - Relapsed or refractory	Once a day (daily) oral administration (dose recommended by doctor in continuous 28 day cycle)	Recruiting without results
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Abbreviations: AML (acute myeloid leukemia), CRs (complete remissions), OR (overall response), MS (median survival) OS (overall survival), PRs (partial remissions).

Safety profile and potency of the Quizartinib

A research found that healthy individuals who took fluconazole or ketoconazole together with quizartinib responded to the combination medication favourably ^[18]. However, 36 of those receiving treatment experienced at least one adverse event (AE), most of which were Grade 1 or moderate. Gastrointestinal difficulties were the most found side effects of quizartinib. The study also found that both fed and fasting healthy volunteers tolerated a single 30-mg dosage of quizartinib well ^[19]. Quizartinib's efficacy in treating resistant or relapsed AML was assessed in the J102 and A103 studies. The results revealed that A103 patients had full remission, but J102 patients had just 75% ^[20]. When quizartinib was administered at dosages as low as 40 mg/day, individuals with FLT3-ITD mutations exhibited better responses. In a phase 2 trial, the risk of mortality was reduced by 24% when compared to chemotherapy ^[15].

Tolerance and ADR of the Quizartinib

In over 750 patients, quizartinib, a single treatment for AML, has been linked to side effects. Gastrointestinal discomfort, myelosuppression, infections, constitutional problems, and bleeding are typical adverse events (AEs). Of particular importance are differentiation syndrome and QTc prolongation. Quizartinib has a dose-dependent dropout rate of 26% as a result of adverse

events. With poor CR rates due to cytopenias brought on by quizartinib's suppression of c-Kit, an essential hematopoietic stem cell factor, the most frequent clinical response is CRc ^[21]. 5% of patients who took VANFLYTA plus chemotherapy encountered significant side events, including febrile neutropenia (11%), according to the QuANTUM-First randomized, double-blind clinical trial. Ten percent of patients experienced fatal adverse events, including as cerebral edema, fungal infections, and sepsis. Sepsis was the most common reason for permanent cessation, which happened in 20% of patients. Neutropenia, thrombocytopenia, and myelosuppression were the most frequent adverse events, and 34% of patients experienced dose reductions or suspensions. Commonly observed anomalies in the laboratory were magnesium, phosphorus, albumin, potassium, and lymphocytes ^[11]. Patients with MDS and MDS/MPN with detectable FLT3 and/or CBL mutations, with or without prior failure to HMA (HMA-F), were enrolled in a phase I/II clinical trial where they received quizartinib at dose levels 1, 2, and 3. Throughout the 28-day DLT study period, no dose-limiting toxicities were found. Constipation, exhaustion, sleeplessness, anorexia, cough, diarrhea, and arthralgia were among the frequent side effects. Anemia, thrombocytopenia, lung infection, skin infection, hyponatremia, and sepsis were among the grade 3–4 adverse events. Observations of arrhythmias included five patients ^[24]. QT interval prolongation, nausea, anemia, exhaustion, vomiting, and diarrhea are among the major side effects of quizartinib medicine. Nonetheless, its toxicity is controlled and it is often well-tolerated. In 32% of the participants in the QuANTUM-R trial, a dose decrease was necessary because of adverse events, lengthening of the QT interval, or other factors. Hematological problems, infections, abnormal electrolyte levels, tiredness, and dyspnea were among the grade ≥ 3 adverse events. Eight percent of patients experienced treatment-emergent adverse events that resulted in withdrawal ^[22]. The National Cancer Institute Common Terminology Criteria were utilized to evaluate adverse events (AEs), and ECGs were obtained during screening. Additionally, physical examinations, vital signs, CBCs, clinical chemistry, and urine analyses were performed both at baseline and during the trial. Quizartinib was evaluated at different dose levels; the majority of adverse events (AEs) were grade 2 and controllable with medication, treatment interruption, and dosage decrease. Anemia, weariness, and a longer ECGQT interval were among the grade 3 AEs. The grade 4 adverse effects were hypoalbuminemia and thrombocytopenia. There was no published mean daily dose (MTD); the MTD was 200 mg/day. In general, quizartinib was well tolerated ^[23].

Conclusion

Quizartinib is marketed as Vanflyta, an oral tyrosine kinase inhibitor used to treat acute myeloid leukemia with FLT3-ITD mutations. It works by blocking the FLT3 receptor tyrosine kinase, thereby inhibiting the growth of leukemia cells. The drug has been approved in regions including the United States, Japan, and the European Union based on its efficacy in clinical trials. Overall, quizartinib's targeted action, survival benefits, and manageable safety profile make it a valuable treatment option for patients with FLT3-ITD-positive AML.

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